

TIKTOK: THE STAGE FOR DIGITAL NATIVES.

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Roland Barthes, in *The Obvious and the Obtuse*, writes that singing is to fantastically enjoy the unified body. But it doesn't always happen. The body, a fundamental element during the process of identity construction, is often excluded from adolescents' performances. The same body, however, becomes the protagonist on TikTok, a social within which a new type of performativity is being defined with respect to which adolescents act naturally.

The goal of the research, which is under development, is to contribute to the growth of good teaching practices for current adolescents. To achieve this, the research is developed through the following questions: what are the aspects of performativity of TikTok related to artistic-musical expressiveness? What are the affordances of TikTok that enable adolescents to use their bodies naturally in online performances? What is the relationship, if there really were, between the gestural aspect of TikTok performances and the technical-expressive vocal aspect? What are the implications of this relationship for music pedagogy in adolescence?

The methodology involves the following steps:

- Content analysis of videos of vocal performances featured on TikTok (in progress);
- TikToker interviews regarding the process leading up to the final performance;
- Case Study: analysis of the gestural relationship of TikTok and voice through *Praat* software and Laban's observation criteria.

Research implication is also connected to the world of artistic practice and performers, worlds that are experiencing a continuous redefinition determined precisely by the impact of social media.

Keywords: TikTok, digital natives, social performativity, music education, vocal pedagogy.

1. Introduction

This article is situated in the early stage of a research project, currently in progress, aimed at exploring the relationships between performative practices on TikTok, focused on popular music, and the artistic and musical expressivity of Generation Z and Generation Alpha. The goal is to outline the potential implications of integrating these forms of performativity into contemporary music education and vocal pedagogy.

The desire to conduct this research stems from the desire to promote music education that can be informed by real-world contexts and, specifically, by the communication methods of so-called digital natives. These methods, on social media, have both multimodal and multimedia dimensions. The hypothesis underlying this study is that this type of communication, in which the body becomes a co-protagonist of the voice, can amplify the technical and expressive possibilities of the singing voice and, consequently, can also contribute to the knowledge of the artistic self.

The purpose of this article is to illustrate the main findings that have emerged from the literature review, in order to lay the initial interpretative foundations for answering the first research question: what are the aspects of performativity of TikTok related to artistic-musical expressiveness?

2. Why TikTok? An overview of the literature review

TikTok was launched in 2016 and, after just a few years, in 2019, it became an app with over 1 billion downloads. The app was mainly downloaded by so-called digital natives, who quickly became the protagonists of a new and significant digital community. For younger generations, TikTok represents a place where they can build relationships with their peers. As developmental psychology teaches us, the peer group plays an important role in the adolescent growth process and it performs irreplaceable functions of identity mirroring and support with the developmental tasks that this ages poses (Bortolotto M., 2009).

In addition, they validate themselves by posting videos and sharing other users' videos. In these videos, they sing, dance or, more generally, show aspects of their daily lives. TikTok is currently the place where Gen Z, and even more so Gen Alpha, spend most of their time. Therefore, it can be stated that social media are influencing 21st century operations, and whether it refers to reference to communications, business practices or education, they are at the center of the modern individual (Williams R., 2022).

First of all, therefore, choosing TikTok rather than another social platform means choosing the environment that digital natives know best, since they were born into a historical context in which digital technology was already popular. This generation, in fact, began using technology from childhood, learning right away, and naturally, to understand its features and ways of use. Furthermore, TikTok stands out from other social media platforms in one fundamental aspect which, when viewed from an educational perspective, takes on particular significance: in order to fully enjoy the platform experience, users must produce content (basically videos). Creative interaction therefore takes precedence over discursive interaction. And sound is a fundamental element of this creative interaction. A relationship based on a shared creative process prevails, rather than a discursive relationship based on the exchange of messages, which is typical of platforms such as Facebook, for example (Marino G., Surace B, 2023).

TikTok presents itself to young people as a virtual stage where one can bring their artistic and musical expressiveness. In this regard, I would like to mention two studies that highlight this very aspect. The first is a study conducted at Northwestern University that analyses "Duets", one of TikTok's signature features, highlighting how they facilitate a creative process that is, in this case, collaborative and social. In this way, TikTok's virtual space offers musicians an additional creative opportunity within a digital social space (O'Tool, K., 2023). The second study, included in my current state of the art, links social performativity and artistic-musical expression. This study was conducted at the University of Hong Kong and looked at the incorporation of TikTok by Filipino musicians into their performances. It found that this encourages the construction of a new logic and a new cultural format that improves musical content and narratives (Tintiangko J., Y.H. Fung A., Leo-Liu J., 2023). Digital cultures are performative cultures, and performativity in its heterogeneous dimensions cannot afford to ignore the forces and effects of digital technologies and their links to human bodies (Leeker et al., 2016). So, recognize this potential, however, is crucial for today's music teachers and, specially, singing teachers.

3. Methodology

Currently, the research design, based on qualitative research, involves three phases:
- **Phase 1:** Content analysis of TikTok performance videos.

This phase, currently underway, consists of:

- **Selection of audio-visual material:** 40 videos of boy/girl singing performances (teenagers) where there is always more than one performer. I selected this type of performance because I would also like to investigate the type of peer relationships that are formed on this platform through performances that are, in fact, shared. The genre performed in these videos, and chosen by me, is pop music. Finally, the locations of these performances are kitchen, bedroom, large parking lots.

- **Qualitative coding:** observation and definition of elements that return in the videos such as, for example, vocal gestures, subtitles, emojis. The purpose of this is to define, in as much detail as possible, the structure of these performances through an analysis of digital ethnography. The digital ethnography studies online interactions, and therefore communities online. It is important for me to investigate this aspect because performances are designed with the response of other users in mind. In most cases, one of the goals of those who perform on this platform is to go viral, reaching a very large audience in a short time.

- Specifically, what I would like to investigate about these performances is the relationship between the gestures of the performances and the technical- expressive vocal aspect. To carry out this analysis, *Praat* software will be used with regard to the vocal aspect, while Laban's observation criteria (Bardacci S., 2002) will be used with regard to gesture analysis. Praat is free software for acoustic analysis of voice and speech. With Praat, it is possible to extrapolate the analysis in graphical form, thus providing a visual representation of the vocal parameters.

Laban, on the other hand, was a choreographer and movement theorist (the fundamentals of the theory of "Labanotation" were expressed in 1928). Laban's intention was to construct a real language capable of describing movement, one that was not "subjective" but had an analytical-functional approach based on a physical-mathematical study of the movement of the body in space. I find it interesting when Laban states that theatrical movement becomes an expression of oneself, a search for oneself, but also a moment of community life. And in my opinion, this is exactly what happens on TikTok among teenagers. The idea is to compare the two analyses and see if there is a gesture associated with a specific vocal technique that recurs in multiple performances and understand whether that type of gesture allows the creation of an image that is functional to sound production, using a specific vocal technique. However, in my opinion, observation alone is not enough to understand this: it is necessary to engage in dialogue with the protagonist of these performances.

- **Phase 2:** Semi-structured interviews with groups of adolescents (e.g. high school students) who use TikTok for their performances plus interview with a famous TikToker. Specifically, I would like to interview Anthony Gargiula who has been using social platforms for his performances since he was 17 years old. He is currently 25 years old.

- **Phase 2.1:** Follow a TikToker for one year (a kind of *365 day challenge*, which is on TikTok) and at the same time a teenager using TikTok. Observe and analyze (with the parameters defined in Phase 1) of day 1 and day 365 videos. I would like to analyze how the development of the technical-expressive vocal aspect can be defined. This could be supported by an autoethnographic research dimension: creation of a TikTok profile where I post daily short performances of myself with the aim of understanding my own development and what I will that might convey for me as a teacher.

- **Phase 3:** designing a teaching path based on approach that considers the results obtained from the first two phases (research implications).

4. Characteristics of the TikTok stage

In this initial phase of the research, thanks to the reference literature on TikTok and the performativity that characterises this platform, and thanks to my observation of the videos I selected, it is possible to deduce some fundamental characteristics of the videos on this platform.

1. **Multimodality:** TikTok performances are based on multiple codes. All performances feature the simultaneous use of images, text, sounds, voice, gestures and movements, all of which contribute to the construction of a narrative that is unique to the performance itself.
2. The **frameless interface** catapults us into the performance. The image, which is not framed by anything, reduces the distance between user and creator, audience and performer, even though we see everything through a screen.
3. **Collective creativity.** Reducing this distance leads to a creative process, which translates into performance, which is shared as it is determined by user feedback in the form of comments, likes and video shares. This allows creators to understand what their audience likes and dislikes and, as a result, to rethink and reformulate their performance.
4. But also **personal creativity.** Personal creativity is expressed in the way the performer interprets and personalises a specific platform format (like *Duet*, *Challenge*). The compromise lies between the standardisation of what goes viral and the performer's personal touch.

• The relevance of the research

The relevance of this research project extends to multiple areas.

1. **Pedagogical-educational area** through the understanding of new reading tools for teaching that is more rooted in the reality of today's adolescents.
2. **Psychological-sociological area.** Investigating the relationship between adolescents and their bodies, which is at the forefront of this platform. Could this exposure be connoted not only in a negative way? Could uploading a video be a tool for validating one's physical appearance? Furthermore, understanding how Gen Z and Gen Alpha perform on TikTok could be a tool for understanding the identity-building process of digital natives.
3. **Artistic practice.** In its first phase, this research aims to investigate the performative and expressive possibilities of the digital platform. On TikTok, before uploading content, there are numerous rehearsals in front of the screen and enormous attention to detail, given the limited time of the performance itself. These numerous rehearsals and such attention could be a prerequisite for an awareness of one's own artistic action (especially with regard to the voice, which originates in a place we cannot see).

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